

TECHNOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING PHYSICS STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH

Mahbuba Holmatova

Lecturer of Namangan State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14241819>

Abstract: This article analyzes modern technologies and methods for developing professional communicative competence in English for physics students. The author shows the role and importance of improving communication competence in professional activities in the educational process. Detailed information is provided on the technologies for developing students' English competence through work on professional terminology and texts related to the subject, for example, the use of distance learning platforms, interactive games, and project-based learning techniques.

Keywords: professional communicative competence, English, physics, technologies, distance learning, interactive methods, project-based learning.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются современные технологии и методы развития профессиональной коммуникативной компетентности на английском языке у студентов-физиков. Автор показывает роль и значение совершенствования коммуникативной компетентности в профессиональной деятельности в образовательном процессе. Подробная информация представлена о технологиях развития английской компетентности студентов посредством работы с профессиональной терминологией и текстами по предмету, например, использование платформ дистанционного обучения, интерактивных игр и методов проектного обучения.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная коммуникативная компетентность, английский язык, физика, технологии, дистанционное обучение, интерактивные методы, проектное обучение.

In higher education institutions around the world, special attention is paid to scientific research on improving professional competence in teaching foreign languages, including improving professional competence in English lessons, free choice of modern teaching methods, linguo-methodical exercises and the use of multimedia educational programs. In countries such as Great Britain (Aston University), USA (Millersville University), South Korea (Seoul National University), Japan (Kyoto University), Finland (University of Helsinki), Latvia (University of Latvia), Russia (Pskov State Pedagogical University), Kazakhstan (Nazarbayev University), improving professional competence in foreign

language teaching methods is recognized as one of the priority tasks in teaching. In order to improve professional competence, systematic work is being carried out to introduce modern pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process, select appropriate exercises aimed at teaching professional and industry terms in English lessons, develop modern educational resources and improve the educational and methodological support for their implementation in practice.

In the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages at the global level, professional competence is recognized as one of the components of students' communicative competence in English, which is aimed at developing and improving their knowledge, skills and abilities in selecting and mastering industry language tools in the educational process. In the process of teaching English, it is important to set a requirement for the development and introduction of new typological educational tasks in the educational process, and to conduct research on teaching based on the mastery of industry terms.

Since the teaching of foreign languages has become one of the important requirements of modern human society in our country, the normative and material and technical base for the use of effective methods in teaching English in higher educational institutions, the organization of teaching based on foreign experience, and the improvement of professional competence of students are being created.

Current methodology of teaching English requires a qualitatively new approach to solving the tasks of improving professional competence of students in this process, ensuring the educational and methodological support of the educational process. After all, teaching physics students professional and technical terms in the teaching of English as a foreign language (TEFL) should be one of the necessary conditions for their future professional and pedagogical activities. This, in turn, requires in-depth study of the English language in integration with specialized and specialized subjects, improvement taking into account didactic foundations, and improvement of communicative competence in the process of teaching English to physics students.

Thus, in order to actively participate in the global knowledge space, master achievements in science, and participate in international scientific projects, it is important for students to acquire communicative competence in English in their professional field. Especially, English is extremely relevant as a means of keeping abreast of scientific research and technological innovations for physics students.

The main goals of studying English in physics are as follows:

- Mastering professional terminology: Correctly pronouncing and understanding concepts and terms related to physics.
- Analyzing scientific texts: Developing the ability to independently read and analyze international scientific articles, textbooks, and technical documents.
- Communication skills: Participating in international conferences, seminars, being active in discussions, and expressing one's thoughts in English.

The possibilities of increasing the effectiveness of improving the professional communicative competence of physics students in English were implemented on the basis of innovative educational technologies in our research. In particular, the experimental work carried out in the educational process using innovative educational technologies (Jigsaw, Podcasting, "Case-study", "SMART", "SWOT", "Insert"), free dialogue and general didactic interactive methods and technologies yielded effective results. Besides, we used distance learning platforms, interactive games, simulations and project-based teaching techniques.

Teaching physics courses in English through interactive games and simulations are effective. Learning English through tools such as interactive simulations to perform physics laboratory experiments in a virtual environment provides practice-based learning. Students learn to communicate in their professional field directly through games. Tools like *Kahoot!* and *Quizlet* can be adapted to reinforce physics terminology and test students' understanding of concepts in English. Gamified learning motivates students to engage actively while reinforcing their professional vocabulary.

Working on a project-based approach to solving physics problems in English develops teamwork among students. At the end of the project, students strengthen their communication and presentation skills by presenting their results. Using these technologies help increase students' ability to understand physics texts in English. Students become prepared to actively participate in international scientific activities and increase their professional competitiveness by developing communication skills.

Improving the professional communicative competence of physics students in English is crucial for their success in a global academic and professional environment. Modern educational technologies offer powerful tools for achieving this goal by combining interactive, practical, and personalized learning experiences. By using tools such as virtual laboratories, CLIL, and collaborative platforms, educators can transform the way physics students learn and use

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

English professionally. Institutions must embrace these innovations to prepare students for the demands of the global scientific community

References:

1. Brown, H. D. (2007). Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. Pearson Education.
2. Coyle, D., Hood, P., & Marsh, D. (2010). CLIL: Content and Language Integrated Learning. Cambridge University Press.
3. Harmer, J. (2015). The Practice of English Language Teaching (5th ed.). Pearson.
4. Singh, M. K. M., & Yunus, M. M. (2019). "Innovation in English Language Teaching: The Integration of Technology in CLIL." Journal of ELT Research, 4(1), 15-27.